

Quality Levels of Generation Z in the Context of Regular Benefit from Gym

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Öz

Bu çalışmanın temel amacı Z Kuşağı bireylerin yaşam kalitesi düzeylerinin spor salonlarından (fitness merkezleri) düzenli faydalanmasına göre farklılaşma düzeylerini ortaya koymaktır. Spor salonlarından düzenli faydalanılması unsuru minimum haftada bir faydalanılması bağlamında değerlendirilmiştir. Bunun yanında Z kuşağı bireylerin yaşam kalitesi düzeylerinin ve at boyutlarının (genel yaşam kalitesi, genel sağlık kalitesi, bedensel alan, ruhsal alan, sosyal alan, çevresel alan) gelire, cinsiyete, medeni duruma ve eğitim düzeyine göre farklılaşma düzeylerini ortaya koymak amaçlanmıştır. Araştırmanın evrenini Antalya ilindeki Z kuşağı (1995-2010) bireyler oluşturmaktadır. Çalışmada spor salonundan faydalanan 150 ve spor salonlarından faydalanmayan 150 olarak toplamda 300 kişiye ulaşılmıştır. 248 adet kabul edilebilir anket verisi değerlendirmeye alınmıştır. Veri toplama aracı olarak demografik bilgi formu ve Dünya Sağlık Örgütü Yaşam Kalitesi ölçeği kısa formu (WHOQOL-BREF-TR) uygulanmıştır. Farklılık analizlerinde One-Way Anova ve T-testi kullanılmıştır. Çalışmada yaşam kalitesi düzeyleri ve bütün alt boyutlarının spor salonlarından faydalanma durumuna göre faydalananlar lehine farklılaştığı görülmüştür. Ayrıca yaşam kalitesi düzeylerinin yüksek geliri olanlar lehine farklılaştığı; cinsiyete göre erkekler lehine farklılaştığı, medeni duruma göre evli olanlar lehine farklılaştığı; eğitim düzeyine göre ise farklılaşma olmadığı görülmüştür. Çalışma bulguları pratik uygulamalar bağlamında çıkarımlar için değerlendirilmesinde önemli hususları barındırmaktadır. Bu çalışmanın en önemli bulgusu yaşam kalitesi düzeyleri ve bütün alt boyutlarının spor salonlarından faydalanma durumuna göre faydalananlar lehine farklılaşma görülmesidir. Dolayısıyla devlet olarak genç bireylerin rekreatif katılıma yönlendirmesini sağlayarak bunu bir politika haline getirmelidir. Geleceğimiz olan gençlerin hem ruhsal hem bedensel hemde çevresel anlamda gelişmesi ülkemizin refahını ve gelişmişlik düzeyini arttıracak gibi huzurlu ve güvenli ortamında sağlayacaktır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Z kuşağı, Yaşam Kalitesi, Spor Salonu (Fitness Merkezi), Spor

Abstract

The main purpose of this study is to reveal the differentiation levels of the quality of life of Generation Z individuals according to their regular use of gyms (fitness centers). The element of regular use of gyms was valued in the context of using a minimum of once a week. In addition, it is aimed to reveal the levels of differentiation of the life quality levels and sub-dimensions (general quality of life, general health quality, physical area, mental area, social area, environmental area) of the Z generation individuals according to income, gender, marital status and education level. The population of this search consists of Z generation (1995-2010) individuals in the province of Antalya. In the study, a total of 300 people were reached, 150 of whom benefited from the gym and 150 who did not use the gymnasium. 248 acceptable survey data were evaluated. Demographic information form and World Health Organization Quality of Life scale short form (WHOQOL-BREF-TR) were used as data collection tools. One-Way Anova and T-test were used for difference analysis. In the study, it was observed that the quality of life levels and all sub-dimensions differed in favor of those who benefited from the gyms. In addition, it was observed that the quality of life levels differed in favor of those with high income, differed in favor of men according to gender, differed in favor of married people according to marital status, and there was no differentiation according to education level.

Keywords: Z Generation, The Quality Of Life, Gyms (Fitness Center), Sport

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Purpose

The main purpose of this study is to reveal the differentiation levels of the life quality levels and sub-dimensions of generation Z individuals according to their regular use of gyms. The element of regular use of gyms was evaluated in the context of using at least once a week. In addition to this main purpose, it is aimed to reveal the differentiation levels of the quality of life of the Z generation individuals according to income, gender, marital status and education level.

Design /Methodology/ Approach

The universe of the research consists of Z generation individuals born in 1995-2010 in Antalya (Yuksekbilgili, 2015). A total of 300 people were reached, 150 people who regularly use the gym and 150 people who do not use the gym regularly. Sample numbers between 200 and 300 are generally considered sufficient in survey type studies in social sciences (Gürbüz ve Şahin, 2014: 128). In this context, in this study, a questionnaire was applied by trained interviewers to willing participants (individuals who use gymnasiums and those who do not) using convenience sampling technique. Questionnaires were administered through face-to-face interviews. 52 questionnaires that were found to be incomplete and inaccurate from the applied questionnaires were not included in the analysis. In this case, a total of 248 participants, 102 women and 146 men, took part in the study voluntarily. The fact that the research was carried out only in Antalya, and the presence of research during the Covid-19 pandemic process constitutes the limitations of the research.

The research is a quantitative research. In the research, data were collected by means of a questionnaire. Statistical analyzes of the data were made by coding the data collected from the participants and transferring them to the SPSS package program. One-Way Anova and T-test were used for difference analysis. Data collection tool is "Whoqol-Bref quality of life scale". In order to measure the quality of life, the Turkish version of the WHOQOL-BREF (World Health Organization Quality of Life Scale Short Form) scale, which was prepared by the World Health Organization with 15 collaborative centers, was applied. The questionnaire type, which has a full and short form as WHOQOL (100 questions) and WHOQOL-BREF, scores individuals' own quality of life (Başaran, Güzel, Sapel, 2005). The WHOQOL-BREF scale, organized as a short form; It includes four sub-areas: physical, psychological, social and environmental. This scale, which was created by experts from 18 countries within the World Health Organization, has a wide range of treatment services, health services, health research and health policy development to help the physician choose an appropriate treatment method (Fidaner vd., 1999).

Findings

In this study, it was observed that the quality of life levels and all sub-dimensions differed in favor of those who benefited from the gyms. In addition, it was observed that the quality of life levels differed in favor of those with high income, differed in favor of men according to gender, differed in favor of married people according to marital status, and there was no differentiation according to education level.

Practical implications

The study findings contain important considerations in their evaluation for inferences in the context of practical applications. The most important finding of this study is that there is a differentiation in favor of the beneficiaries according to the level of quality of life and all sub-dimensions of using the gym. Therefore, as a state, this should be made a policy by encouraging young people to participate in recreational participation. The development of young people, who are our future, both spiritually, physically and environmentally, will increase the welfare and development level of our country, as well as provide a peaceful and safe environment. Education will be done not only by educating the mind but also by educating and resting the body, thus raising healthier adults of the future. In developed countries, death and birth rates are low as significant investments are made in awareness and health. As a recreation business, it will also be beneficial for young individuals to go to the gyms in terms of bringing athletes to our country in sports competitions. Considering that the quality of life of individuals participating in recreational activities is high, it is thought that the state will reduce health

expenditures to a minimum.

Originality/ value

When the literature is reviewed, many studies have been conducted on the level of quality of life. However, no study has been found on examining the quality of life of individuals of the Z generation (1995-2010 birth years) who regularly use and do not benefit from gyms. Therefore, it is thought that it will be an important reference for future studies and will shed light on the studies, and in this context, it will be beneficial to repeat this research in a more comprehensive way.

1. INTRODUCTION

With the influence of the Renaissance and the discovery of new sea routes, humanism movements and new inventions brought vitality to people's lives. Structural change of cities accelerated thinking elements predominated. Various arts, poetry and literary performances, as well as philosophical and theoretical studies, have taken shape many activities such as picnics and playing various games. Thanks to the improvement of working conditions, especially technological developments, the time allocated for rest and entertainment in the pre-industrial revolution periods has been increased. However, at the beginning of the industrial revolution, leisure time left over from work was thought of as waste and laziness. However, these ideas have changed over time. It has been accepted that leisure time provides mental and physical relaxation outside of work (Gündüz, 1998).

With the invention of the steam engine in 1765, the industrialization movement began. 18th century late and 19th century Towards the beginning, radical changes took place in the social lives of people. The time period in which they spent their rest and entertainment activities was affected. It is normal for societies to influence each other in shaping the lives of cultural backgrounds and interactions. It is normal for societies to influence each other in shaping the lives of cultural backgrounds and interactions. Therefore, the effects of pre-Anatolian Turkish communities, the Byzantine Empire, the Ottoman Empire, Islam and Western societies appear on the formation of people's lives in Turkey (Karakuş, 1997). Before coming to Anatolia, the people of Turkish society were engaged in agriculture, animal husbandry and made preparations for war. Apart from these, war preparations turned into a game, and many games were performed, especially on horses. There were weddings, feasts, ceremonies, celebrations, where meals were eaten collectively (Tayga, 1990). The lifestyles of the Turks who converted to Islam have changed drastically in the 11th century. The recreational lifestyle has varied and enriched. Mosque visits, lay visits, quran reading, mawlid, holiday visits and entertainments, Ramadan entertainments and festivities, religious conversations are just a few of them. The effect of the ahî-order tradition in the Ottoman Empire is seen in the form of entertainment-oriented activities. These include activities such as going to recreation areas, baths, coffee houses, hunting and shooting (Sezgin, 1987).

The increasing rapid industrialization and urban migration of the Turkish society in the Republic of Turkey has made work and non-work time distinctive. It has been emphasized how the holiday will be used to evaluate free time with employees and urbanization. In this period, there has been a change in the activities about how they spend their free time. For example, going to the seaside instead of going to the garden in the summer months has taken the place of going to the highlands (Karakucuk, 1999). In the work of the State Planning Organization (SPO) in 1993, it seems that there are various layers in Turkey and their leisure time is common and abundant. And it has been researched how to use this excess free time in Turkey. Therefore, making use of these free times carries more value for a developing country like Turkey. Today, this has become passive (DPT, 1994: 132). Watching television, listening to the radio, going to the cinema, to the theater, playing games, hanging out with friends, surfing the Internet on Facebook, Instagram, YouTube and spending time on social platforms are examples of these. It is the activities done to achieve spiritual and physical vitality in order to perform activities and actions that connect the individual to life, which are relaxing, entertaining, occupied or pleasurable, and to participate in these activities. (Yücel, 1998). There are studies in the literature that the individuals who use the gyms theoretically affect the general quality of life and health in physical, mental, social and environmental areas (Parker, 1981, cited in Polat, 2016; Arslantaş et al., 2006; Özmete,

2010; Knöchel, 2012; Lindstrom, B. & Kohler, L., 1991; Turgut, 2010; Bilgiç, 2009). However, no study has been found in the literature on the effects of Z-generation individuals on the quality of life of gymnasiums. In this direction, the main purpose of this study is to reveal the differentiation levels of the life quality levels and sub-dimensions of Generation Z individuals according to their regular use of gyms. The element of regular use of gyms was evaluated in the context of using at least once a week. In addition to this main purpose, it is aimed to reveal the differentiation levels of the quality of life of the Z generation individuals according to income, gender, marital status and education level.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Leisure Concept

This concept, which continued with industrialization, brought new meanings with it. This concept of "non-working time" has been described as "informal space" where people can evaluate as they wish. In the literature, "leisure time" "free time" or "free time" refers to this area. Since it is thought that time will not be empty in our country, the concept of "free time" is more preferred than the concept of "free time". However, there seems to be a difference in the real meaning of the word "free time" included in the concept of "leisure time". "Free" means "with his head tied" in Persian. Thus, free time refers to a programmed and regulated time rather than non-working time. The opposite of the word free is the word "serbaz". Turkish synonyms mean "empty" and "empty". Thus, it seems appropriate to the dictionary and etymology to use the concept of "leisure time" instead of "free time" as non-work time (Doğan, 2002).

2.2. Concept of Sport

Sport as an evaluation element of leisure time is one of the important elements evaluated today. According to the literature, there is more than one definition of sport. Sport; It is a concept that a person does in his/her free time or as a whole, with or without tools, with certain rules in order to improve his/her own abilities in his/her environment, socializing the individual, providing spiritual and physical development, and being in a competitive element as well as culturally (Aracı, 2006).

TDK defines sport as all of the movements performed according to some rules performed individually or collectively in order to improve the body or mind (tdk.gov.tr, 2019).

2.3. Concept of Gym (Fitness Halls)

They are places that appeal to individuals who are interested in sports and have needs. In other words, it is the place where preparations and exercises are made in order to increase the sports activities to the desired extent. These are sports facilities operated by public or private enterprises, which are allowed by the state, that meet the needs of the people who benefit from the service, as well as the athlete, the trainer, the individual who receives the service and the people who provide the service, such as healthy clean, changing cabins, showers, toilets, heating-cooling, lighting, ventilation (Akça, 2012: p.20).

2.4. Generation Concept

When the literature on generation is examined, generation is a concept that has more than one meaning. This term, which is generally used in the literature of social sciences, means "the community of people who were born in approximately the same years, shared the conditions of the same age, therefore similar troubles and destinies, and were responsible for similar duties" according to TDK (2020). In addition to this, it is used in social sciences in the sense of "The group of individuals forming the age groups of approximately twenty-five, thirty years, belly, generation, abdomen, generation".

When the literature is examined, there is no definite consensus on the classification of the histories of the concept of generation. However, it is seen that the classification as date is in recent date ranges. There are

differences in the behaviors and characteristics of generations in different countries due to the social, economic and environmental factors of generations with common characteristics (Kuyucu, 2017: p.853).

On the other hand, with the development of technology and globalization, national and regional differences are disappearing in individuals belonging to the same generation living in different parts of the world. The research conducted by Yüksekbilgili (2015) shows that; It has been determined that there is 3 years between the start date of the Y generation in Turkey and the onset date of the Y generation in the USA. While the start date of the Y generation is accepted as 1980 in the USA, it is thought that there is a 3-year difference due to the delay in accessing technology since the technology arrived in Turkey in the mid-1980s (Yüksekbilgili, 2015: p.261).

In the light of the research conducted by Yüksekbilgili (2015), in this research, the beginning date of the Y generation will be accepted as 1983 and the order of the generation chronology, Baby boom generation, 1946-1964; Generation X 1965-1982; millennials 1983-1995; Generation Z is organized on the basis of 1996-2010.

Individuals born between 1946 and 1964 are in the baby boom generation. As the name suggests, 75.8 million babies, which constituted 40 percent of the population of the USA in 1964, were born in a 19-year period (Green, 2006: p.8). Different names have been used for this generation. These are names such as The Sixties Generation, Flower Children, The Me Generation, Yuppies (Green, 2006: p.4).

X generation individuals born between 1965-1982 are also referred to as "babybuster" in some sources due to the decrease in high birth rates in the baby boom generation (Celek et al., 1996: p.20).

The concept of Generation Y, which takes its name from the English word (Why?), refers to the generation between 1981 and 1995. Since the nature of individuals born in this period is constantly questioning, this name was chosen for this generation. The term millennials was later cited by writers and historians Neil Howe and William Strauss in their 2000 "Rise of the Millennials" (The Rise of the Millennials), although the term is more catchy, noted by Stilman and Stillman (1996). Other names given to Generation Y are Digital Generation and Futures, Generation Next, Net Gen, Echo Boomer and Baby Busters (Stilman and Stillman, 2019: p.16).

Individuals born between the start year 1995 and the end year 2010 are considered to be the Z generation (Horn, 2013: p.12). Various names have also been used for the Z generation. Some of these are names such as Gen Z, Zeds, IGen (internet generation), Digital Natives (Ericsson Consumerlab, 2012: p.3; GrailResearch, 2011: p.2).

Individuals in this generation, who witnessed negative developments such as global crisis, terrorism and environmental events, were affected. In addition to these, the widespread use of the internet and social media, the development and spread of devices such as mobile phones, tablets and computers are among the developments that affect individuals (Grail Research Report, 2011: p.3). Since it is easy to access similar opportunities and services in the globalizing world, it can be said that the individuals in this generation are the first global generation (Havas People, 2014: p.12).

2.5. The Concept of Quality of Life

A study on "Quality of Life", which was first used by Elkinton in 1966, was initiated by the World Health Organization in the early 1980s to measure and conceptualize this concept. According to the definition of the World Health Organization in terms of health, quality of life is how individuals perceive the values and cultures that they personally experience with their wishes, life expectations, goals and relational sense in their life. In other words, the individual can be described as its own perspective and concerns, standards and expectations in its life, which is related to its goals, within the culture and values it lives in (Top et al., 2003).

As with demographic factors, the income status of individuals and families is one of the factors affecting the quality of life. According to the studies, it is seen that individuals with high income levels have higher quality of life than those with low levels of life (Veenhoven & Dumludağ, 2015). The main reason for this is that individuals with a high income level are more likely to achieve what they want than individuals with a

low income level. Accordingly, it is seen that the quality of life of individuals who can reach the things they want in their lives increases (Dumludağ, 2011).

Gender, which is one of the individual elements, is one of the elements that show the quality of life of humanity. The effects on gender vary from society to society, from culture to culture. According to a study conducted in Sweden, it is seen that the life score of women is lower than that of men due to differences arising from social and psychological effects such as workplace health status and lifestyle (Bingefors & Isacson, 2004).

In the study conducted by Miller and Dishon in Israel in 2006, it was determined that the general quality of life of men was lower than that of women. The differentiation of male and female inequality in developed and developing countries affects the quality of life due to the negative effects of gender (Kangal, 2013). According to some researchers, no significant correlation was found between quality of life and gender. It has been determined that gender is not effective in living alone, and that there are significant relationships as a result of the evaluation of many demographic characteristics as well as this variable (Koçak, 2016).

When the literature is examined, it has been determined that there is a link between the concept of marriage and the concept of quality of life. Studies have shown that married individuals are happier than individuals who have never been married, separated, or widowed (Parker et al., 2003; Avcı & Pala, 2004). Married individuals seem to have more future expectations than individuals living alone, and this is a factor affecting their quality of life (Luttik et al., 2016).

One of the factors affecting the quality of life is that people with higher education levels generally have higher income and status. However, according to some studies, it has been stated that as the education level of the people increases, it increases in direct proportion with the quality of life. On the other hand, according to some studies, it is seen that there is no increase in the quality of life of individuals (Kangal, 2013; Dumludağ, 2011; Gençoğlu & Yılmaz, 2014). For example, in the study conducted by Gündoğar (2007), the fact that individuals studying at university study in departments they do not want and that are not related to their abilities and interests negatively affect their life satisfaction and quality.

According to many studies, it has been determined that there is a connection between the age factor, which is one of the quality of life, and the demographic characteristics of the individuals. Quality of life should not be taken as a measure because it does not only cover a certain age range. For example, while it constitutes an indicator of quality of life for the elderly, it differs for different age groups (Boylu and Paçacıoğlu, 2016: p.140). It has been determined that health problems arise with the aging of individuals, however, there is a decrease in the socialization of elderly individuals (Lehto et al., 2015; Timur & Akay, 2017). Quality of life decreases in individuals between the ages of 30-35. The reason for this is the intense efforts of individuals to survive in this busy period (Dumludağ, 2011). The age factor affects the thoughts, behaviors and attitudes of individuals during their childhood and youth. As their age increases, the needs of individuals differ in different age ranges. The cultures that children acquire in the environments in which they grow up, shape their lives and the quality of life of their families determines the quality of life of their children. During childhood and adolescence, families have a great responsibility. Individuals should observe the behaviors in their families and social environments well and act accordingly (Totan & Yoldem, 2007).

The proverb "Health is the beginning of every job" actually states the importance and place of health in the quality of life of individuals. Human is an individual and social being. The individual lives as a whole with the society it lives in and the social environment. According to Calisir, satisfaction with quality of life is not only individual, but also all social and societal characteristics that affect one's life. For example, individuals who are happy in their business life reflect this in their private life. Individuals who are good and peaceful in their work, home and private life increase the satisfaction of their work, home and private lives. This situation constantly affects each other in the cycle. Individuals who are good and happy can overcome problems in their work, social and private life more easily. It is seen that they are physically and psychologically healthier. The quality of life rates of healthy people can be high (Çalışır, 2012). The activities they do in their spare time are one of the most important elements that improve themselves as well as increase the quality of life of individuals. It helps individuals to discover, renew and reveal themselves in their spare and free time (Aslan

et al., 2012: p.24). In their leisure time, individuals evaluate their spare time outside of work, family and social activities according to their individual wishes and needs (Mansuroğlu, 2002: p.53). Leisure activities, which vary from person to person, vary from country to country, from society to society. According to the studies conducted on adolescents, it is seen that they spend more of their free time on the computer and the Internet. (Aslan et al., 2012, p.29). It is seen that the evaluation of their spare time by reading books is less (Aksaçlıoğlu & Yılmaz, 2007: p.17). In the research conducted with elderly people, it has been shown that leisure activities such as listening to the radio, reading, being interested in hobbies, watching television, visiting relatives, friends and neighbors, as well as going to places such as cinema, theater, museum, etc. have an important place in the quality of life of individuals (Çakır et al., 2013, p.474).

According to some studies in the literature, it is seen that individuals' interest in physical and sports activities increases during adolescence (Salmon et al., 2007, p.144). Doing sports during this period, most importantly, helps their lives to be better in terms of health. According to studies conducted between adolescents with a sedentary lifestyle and individuals who regularly do sports and make it a habit, it is seen that adolescent individuals who do sports have a higher quality of living and life (Casey, 2016, p.1).

In line with the explanations above, the following hypotheses have been developed. The first hypothesis contains six sub-hypotheses. The hypotheses developed as a result of the evaluation of the data collected with the help of the prepared questionnaire were tested. Below are the hypotheses of the research, respectively.

H1: The quality of life of the Z generation individuals differs according to their regular use of gyms.

H1a: The "general quality of life" of the Z generation individuals differs according to their regular use of gyms.

H1b: The "general health quality" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their regular use of gyms.

H1c: The "bodily space" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their regular use of gyms.

H1d: The "spiritual field" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their regular use of gyms.

H1e: The "social space" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their regular use of gyms.

H1f: The "environmental space" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their regular use of gyms.

H2: The "quality of life" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their income levels.

H3: The "quality of life" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their genders.

H4: The "quality of life" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their marital status.

H5: The "quality of life" levels of the Z generation individuals differ according to their education level.

3. METHODS AND FINDINGS

This study is a quantitative research. In the research, data were collected by means of a questionnaire. Questionnaires were administered through face-to-face interviews. 52 questionnaires that were found to be incomplete and inaccurate from the applied questionnaires were not included in the analysis. In this case, a total of 248 participants, 102 women and 146 men, took part in the study voluntarily. Demographic information form and World Health Organization Quality of Life scale short form (WHOQOL-BREF-TR) were used as data collection tools. Statistical analyzes of the data were made by coding the data collected from the participants and transferring them to the SPSS package program. One-WayAnova and T-test were used for difference analysis. The data obtained from the scales used in the research were entered into the computer environment and analyzed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 27.00 program. Data found to be incomplete and inaccurate were not included in the analyses. In addition, before the analysis, the empty items in the data set were determined and the average values were assigned for the missing data. After this process, the total scores and sub-scores of the scales used were calculated. While evaluating the data, descriptive statistical methods (number, percentage, frequency, mean) were used. It was assumed that the sample should show a normal distribution in order to apply parametric test methods to the evaluation of the data (Kalaycı, 2010). In order to evaluate the normality of the distributions for the obtained scores, the skewness and kurtosis values of the data were examined. In order to determine whether the variables used in

the study had a normal distribution, skewness and kurtosis values were examined. Kalaycı (2010) stated that if the skewness and kurtosis measure take values between -3 and +3, it will show a normal distribution.

The kurtosis and skewness values of the scale used in the research are given in the table below. Along with ensuring normality, the use of parametric methods was preferred in the analysis of the data. Difference analyzes were conducted to determine whether the quality of life levels and sub-dimensions of generation Z individuals differ according to their regular use of gyms. In the same way, difference analyzes were conducted to determine whether the quality of life levels of the Z generation individuals differed by gender, marital status, income, education level.

Table 1 shows the results of the Skewness and Kurtosis Values of the Quality of Life Levels and Sub-Dimensions of Generation Z Individuals.

Table 1. Skewness and Kurtosis Values of Quality of Life Levels and Sub-Dimensions of Generation Z Individuals

Variable	Skew	Kurtosis
LQL	-0,102	-0,552
GQL	-0,27	-0,173
GHQ	-0,257	-0,4
BA	-0,261	-,505
SF	-0,156	-0,633
SA	-0,212	-0,33
EA	-0,16	-0,348

Note: LQL= Level of Quality of Life; GQL = General Quality of Life; GHQ= General Health Quality; BA= Bodily Area; SF= Spiritual Field; SA= Social Area; EA= Environmental Area

The internal consistency values for the reliability analysis of the scales (Cronbach's Alpha) are given in the table below. If Cronbach's Alpha reliability values are greater than 0.6, the scale can be considered quite reliable (Akgül & Çevik, 2003).

Table 2. Alpha Values of Quality of Life Levels and Sub-Dimensions of Generation Z Individuals

Variable	Cronbach Alpha Values
LQL	0,922
BA	0,787
SF	0,817
SA	0,781
EA	0,606

3.1. Descriptive Statistics

Demographic information and other descriptive data are included in the table below.

Table 3. Demographics and Other Descriptive Data

		Frequency	Percent %	Cumulative Percentage
Gender	Female	102	41,1	41,1
	Male	146	58,9	100
	Total	248	100	
Marital status	Married	8	3,2	3,2
	Single	240	96,8	100
	Total	248	100	
Education Status	High School	187	75,4	75,4

	Associate degree	36	14,5	89,9
	Degree	18	7,3	97,2
	Master	4	1,6	98,8
	Doctorate	3	1,2	100
	Total	248	100	
Income	0-4000	56	22,6	22,6
	4001-7000	80	32,3	54,8
	7001-10000	60	24,2	79
	10001-13000	29	11,7	90,7
	130001 and over	23	9,3	100
	Total	248	100	
Regular use of gyms	Yes	109	44	44
	No	139	56	100
	Total	248	100	
Attendance time of Gyms	0-1 Yıl	66	26,6	60,6
	1-3 Yıl	26	10,5	82,6
	4 year and over	17	6,9	98,2
	Total	109	44	
	Vacant	139	56	
Total		248	100	

As can be seen in the table above, 102 participants were female and 146 were male. 240 people are single, 8 people are married. Among the participants, there are 56 people in the 0-4000 income group, 80 people in the 4001-7000 income group, 60 people in the 7001-10.000 income group, 29 people in the 10.001-13.000 income group, and 23 people in the 13.001 and above income group. In the education group, there are 187 high school graduates, 36 associate degree graduates, 18 degree graduates , 4 masters graduates and 3 doctorate graduates. In the group of participants who use the gym regularly, "yes" is 109 people, "no" is 139 people. When the participation period is examined, 66 people are in the 0-1 year group, 26 people are in the 1-3 years group, and 17 people are in the 4 years and above group.

3.2. Anova and T-Test Results

The table below shows the summary results of the t-test based on regular use of the gym for the sub-dimensions of quality of life.

Table 4. The T-Test of the Level and Sub-Dimensions of Quality of Life based on Regular Use of Gyms Summary Table

	LQL	GQL	GHQ	BA	SF	SA	EA
Group 1: Yes(n:109)	3,66(0,55)	3,29(1,1)	3,86(0,94)	3,85(059)	3,56(0,63)	3,6(0,79)	3,57(0,66)
Group 2: No(n:139)	3,22(0,69)	2,91(1,07)	3,39(1,02)	3,42(0,75)	2,91(0,81)	3,28(0,86)	3,36(0,8)
t- values	5,49	3,47	3,71	5,00	6,89	5,09	2,16
p-values	0,000	0,001	0,000	0,000	0,000	0,002	0,031

The table below shows the summary table of the Anova and T test results based on the quality of life of the Z generation individuals.

Table 5. Anova and T Test Results Based on Quality of Life Levels of Generation Z Individuals Summary Table

Gender	YKD	
	Grup1: Female (n:102)	3,18 (0,66)
	Grup2: Male (n:146)	3,58 (0,62)
t-value		4,88

	p- value	0,000
Marital Status	Grup1: Single (n:8)	3,4(0,67)
	Grup2:Married (n:240)	3,81(0,39)
	t- value	2,17
	p- value	0,045
Regular (at least 1) Gym Use per week	Grup1: Yes (n:109)	3,66(0,55)
	Grup2: No (n:139)	3,22(0,69)
	t- value	5,49
	p- value	0,000
Income	Group 1: (n:16)	3,08(0,63)
	Group 2: (n:69)	3,33(0,61)
	Group 3: (n: 82)	3,5(0,65)
	Group 4: (n:84)	3,67(0,65)
	Group 5:(n:61)	4,02(0,45)
	F- value	11,778
	p- value	0,000
	Post-Hoc	Group1<Groups 3,4,5 Groups 1,2,3 <Group 5
Education Status	Group 1: (n:187)	3,38(0,67)
	Group 2: (n:36)	3,52(0,59)
	Group 3: (n: 18)	3,59(0,73)
	Group 4: (n:4)	3,45(0,66)
	Group 5:(n:3)	3,18(1,16)
	F- value	0,752
	p- value	0,557
	Post-Hoc	-

A statistically significant difference was found in favor of the yes group according to regular use of the gym in all of the life quality levels and sub-dimensions of the Z generation individuals. Therefore, hypotheses H1, H1a, H1b, H1c, H1d, H1e and H1f were accepted.

As a result of the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), which was conducted to determine whether the sub-dimensions of the quality of life scale of the Z generation individuals of the sample group differ significantly according to income, the difference between the arithmetic means of the groups was found to be significant. Therefore, the H2 hypothesis was accepted. It has been determined that the mentioned difference is negative for the 0-4000 income group between all groups except the 0-4000 income group and the 4001-7000 income group. It was determined that the said difference between all groups except for the income group of 13.000 and above and the income group of 10.001-13.000 was realized in favor of the income group of 13.001 and above.

A statistically significant difference was found in favor of men according to gender in the quality of life of the Z generation individuals. Therefore, the H3 hypothesis was accepted.

A statistically significant difference was found in favor of married individuals according to the marital status of the quality of life of the Z generation individuals. Therefore, the H4 hypothesis was accepted.

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether the sub-dimensions of the quality of life scale of the Z generation individuals who constitute the sample group differ significantly according to their educational status. As a result, the difference between the arithmetic means of the groups was not significant. Therefore, the H5 hypothesis was rejected.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The main purpose of this study is to reveal the differentiation levels of the quality of life of Generation Z individuals according to their regular use of gyms. The element of regular use of gyms was evaluated in the context of using at least once a week. In addition, in this study, it was aimed to reveal the differentiation levels

of Z generation individuals' quality of life levels according to income, gender, marital status and education level.

41.1% of the individuals participating in the study were female and 58.9% were male. Marital status was found to be 3.2% unmarried and 96.8% single. It was observed that 75.4% of the individuals participating in our study were high school graduates, 14.5% associate degree, 7.3% undergraduate, 1.4% graduate and 1.2% doctorate graduates. It is seen that the income status of the participants is 22.6% 0-4000, 32.3% 4001-7000, 24.2% 7001-10000, 11.7% 10001-13000 and 9.3% 13001 and above. In the case of regular use of gyms, it was found that 44% of the participants regularly use it, while 56% do not use it regularly. The duration of participation in the gyms of the participants was seen as between 0-1 years in 26.6%, between 1-3 years in 10.5% and 4 years and above in 6.9%.

In this study, a statistically significant difference was found in favor of those who benefit from the gym according to the status of regular use of the gym in all of the life quality levels and sub-dimensions of the Z generation individuals. According to the studies of [Kıvanç \(2016\)](#) and [Kürklü \(2014\)](#), it was determined that individuals who do physical activity have higher quality of life rates than individuals who do not. Similarly, it has been observed that the physical, psychological, social and environmental quality of life rates of individuals who regularly do a physical activity for 30 or 60 minutes for 3 days are at higher levels than those who do not. And a significance was found between environmental and quality of life ([Elmas, 2018](#)). Therefore, the results of these studies and the results of our study are in the same direction.

In this study, it was determined that high-income individuals have higher quality of life perceptions compared to lower-income individuals. Similarly, [Şahin \(2001\)](#) and [Ay et al. \(2007\)](#) found that there is a positive relationship between income scores and quality of life scores in their research. [Güngör et al., \(2007\)](#) found in their study that the quality of life social field scores of individuals with stable income expenditures are higher than those with unstable income expenses. Likewise, [Musaoğlu \(2008\)](#) states in his study that the quality of life of those with a good income level is also good. In the study conducted by [Sarı et al. \(2007\)](#), it was observed that the quality of life of high school schools with high socio-economic levels is high. And with this, it has been observed that students in high school perceive the quality of life more positively as the grade levels begin to rise ([Sarı et al., 2007, p.297](#)). Accordingly, it can be said that there is a relationship between income status and quality of life. Therefore, the findings of this study are in parallel with the studies in the literature.

When studies examining the relationship between quality of life and gender are examined, it is seen that there are differences according to countries, communities and cultures. In a study conducted in Sweden on this subject, it was determined that female individuals have a lower perception of quality of life than male individuals ([Bingefors & Isacson, 2004](#)). It is stated that this different result may be caused by mental and environmental reasons such as working conditions, health status and lifestyle of individuals. In the BELLA study conducted in Germany, it was stated that the level of life satisfaction of individuals between the ages of 14 and 17 was lower than female individuals in physical, psychological and environmental areas ([Sieberer et al., 2008](#)). Similarly, in a study conducted in Germany in 2007, the quality of life perception level was measured and it was determined that male individuals had higher life satisfaction than female individuals ([Goldbeck et al., 2007](#)). In the study conducted by Lee et al. in Taiwan in 2008, it was seen that male students' total quality of life scores and their sub-dimensions, physical, mental and individual areas, were better than female students ([Lee et al., 1995](#)). According to the study conducted with children studying at school in Finland, it was stated that the mental domain scores of male individuals were better than female individuals ([Laaksonen et al., 2008](#)). In this study, a statistically significant difference was found in favor of men in terms of quality of life. Therefore, it shows parallelism with the studies in the literature.

In the study, a statistically significant difference was determined in favor of married individuals in the quality of life of Generation Z individuals according to marital status. In [Koçoğlu's \(2009\)](#) study, the relationship between marital status and quality of life was examined. It was found that those whose marital status was single got the highest score in quality of life, while those whose marital status was widowed got the

lowest score (Koçoğlu, 2009).

In this study, it was determined that quality of life levels did not differ according to education level. According to the report of the World Health Quality of Life, it is stated that the education of young individuals positively affects their education and training life. As a result, it is stated that there is an increase in quality of life levels. In addition, according to many studies, it is seen that education is important and the quality of life of children who grow up in families with education is high. It is thought that the low educational level of the parents and the level of each other are effective in the low quality of life of the children (Eser et al., 2008; Jirojanakul et al., 2003; Spurrier et al., 2003). Therefore, the findings of this study are not similar to the findings of the studies in the literature.

The study findings contain important considerations in their evaluation for inferences in the context of practical applications. The most important finding of this study is that there is a differentiation in favor of the beneficiaries according to the level of quality of life and all sub-dimensions of using the gym. Therefore, the state should make this a policy by encouraging young people to participate in recreational participation. The development of young people, who are our future, both spiritually, physically and environmentally, will increase the welfare and development level of our country, as well as provide a peaceful and safe environment. Education will be done not only by training the mind, but also by training and resting the body, and will also raise healthier adults of the future. Since significant investments are made in awareness and health in developed countries, death and birth rates are low. As a recreation business, it will be beneficial for young individuals to go to sports halls, to bring athletes to our country in sports competitions. Considering the high quality of life of individuals participating in recreational activities, it is thought that the state will minimize health expenditures.

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